

COMPARATIVE HARDNESS ANALYSIS ON NIGERIAN MARKET WOOD COMPOSITE (PLYWOOD)

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Abstract: Information on hardness test results on wood composites (plywood) in Nigerian market needed by stakeholders to prevent loss of revenue that may arise due to choice of inappropriate wood composites (plywood) for numerous needs as a result of non-availability of such data was explored. To establish their hardness, most frequently sought after wood composites (plywood) were identified, out of which the top three were subjected to test after selection. Each of the samples as required by the Leeds Hardness Tester was prepared and tested four times on the machine for a mean. Plots on the hardness of the samples were ensued by computer program from the generated data. Results show that Caledonian attained aggregate average hardness of 407.5 Leeds Hardness Test (HLD), View Point attained aggregate average hardness of 456.5 HLD while Plywood EQ attained aggregate average hardness of 459.25 HLD. Statistical analysis show that Plywood EQ is 0.6024% and 12.6993% harder than View Point and Caledonian respectively. The difference in hardness between Plywood EQ and View Point is small compared to the difference in hardness between Plywood EQ and Caledonian which is as much as 51.75 HLD. Choice of suitable wood composites (plywood) based on their hardness would be informed by this novel revelation. Biomedical engineers as well as other stake holders should utilize this in the development of their products. Attention in future research should be geared towards hardness tests of marine board wood composites, medium-density fibreboard (MDF) and high-density fibreboard (HDF) in Nigerian market.

Keyword: Brinell Hardness test, Durometer Testing, Indentation Hardness testing, Indentation Testing, Leed Hardness Test, Material Hardness Testing, Material Testing, Mechanical Testing, Rockwell Hardness Test, Scleroscope Testing, Surface Hardness Testing, Vickers Hardness.

I. Introduction

Background of the Study

The global plywood market valued at USD 50.2 billion in 2024 is expected to grow from 2025 with projection to reach USD 74.5 billion by 2033 as noted by (FMRL, 2025) at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) estimate of 4.5%. Even as plywood remains a vital engineered wood product extensively used across furniture, construction and packaging industries in Nigeria, forestry products industrial goods exports in the 1950's, 1960's and 1970's were once enjoyed by Nigeria as noted by (Ogunwusi, 2012). It is unfortunate to note that as at present, Nigeria remains heavily dependent on wood composite (plywood) imports, despite its abundant raw materials and a fast-growing domestic market. Wood composites are different derivative wood products. They are normally obtained through the processes of binding the particles, strands, boards, or fibers of wood together. Similar composite products can also be made from vegetable fibers using lignin-containing materials with chemical additives enabling the integration of polymer and wood flour while helping facilitate optimal processing conditions. Such materials could be rye and wheat straw, sugar cane residue, hemp stalks e.t.c. and due to an excellent combination of mechanical, thermal and acoustic properties together with a competitive price, particle and fiberboards are widely used in the building industry as eco-friendly solutions to wood with increasing uses in thermal insulators, ceiling boards, wall partitions, e.t.c. (Garcia-Garcia, et al 2018). Achieved using adhesives, wood composites are engineered to certain specifications resulting in a material that can have diverse applications. Interestingly, it is obvious to note that wood composites can be created using smaller trees, wood waste materials and hence reduce the need to fell old-growth forests. Garcia-Garcia, et al (2018) Studied the production of highly environmentally-friendly fiberboards by hot-press molding using *Posidonia oceanica* wastes and a partially biobased epoxy resin as binder with the results revealing that there is a remarkable improvement of the mechanical properties with combination of the alkali treatment followed by silanization.

In terms of challenges associated with it, higher fire hazards could be experienced when wood composite is compared to solid wood products as a result of higher chemical heat content and melting properties. Most cheap and common resins usually used in the composites and made with urea-formaldehyde bonded products release toxic formaldehyde in the finished products forming a strong apprehension with wood composite use. Wood composites have numerous advantages, though the process of their manufacture as it relates to solid timber demands for extra primary energy. This is in addition to the humidity-induced warping which is not common in solid woods by some fiber-based and particle based composite woods when they are exposed to moisture. Despite all these challenges stated it is interesting to note that the demand for wood composite is on the rise as projected by the earlier statistics due to remarkable improvement on esthetic and mechanical properties of the resulting composites. Failure of form boards frameworks from wood composites (plywood) especially while the concrete is still not yet set shortly after casting of concretes has been a major source of concern to the construction industry (Ilo, Ajibo, and Dim, 2025a).

It was revealed from the study of inflation trend pattern and its impact on Nigeria's economy that the purchasing power of the Nigerian currency, Naira was seen to be decreasing a revelation that the economy especially building materials market is badly hit by the inflation, (Barguma, et al. 2022). A very strong relationship has been found to exist between building materials prices and rate of residential development following their quest to assess the effect of building materials cost on housing development in Owerri, Imo state, eastern region of Nigeria, (Igboekulie, Monye, and Joseph, 2022). Analyzing the inflation rate and the prices of building materials in Benin city, from a correlation analysis the prices of the building materials had a direct relationship with the inflation rate in Nigeria thus the cause for the high cost of building materials as recorded by (Obaedo, 2024). This x-rayed inflation as the most influential factor responsible for increase in the cost of building materials.

Material Hardness Testing

Materials hardness testing simply is a method employed to determine a material's resistance to scratching, indentation or even deformation. It is simply a test conducted to ascertain the actual resistance exhibited by materials to permanent deformation by penetration of another harder material. Objectively, material hardness testing is a mechanical test for material properties which are used in materials development, structural analysis and engineering design and development. This is typically achieved by pressing a harder material into the surface of the tested material. Basically, the depth of penetration taken as the size of the resulting indentation is measured and subsequently converted into a hardness value. This value is what indicates how well the material can resist deformation that is permanent. A number hardness tests exists. Leed Hardness Test adopted in this research is a dynamic impact test that measures the rebound of a small impactor (indenter) to determine the hardness (HLD). For Brinell Hardness Test, a hardened steel or carbide ball indenter is used to create an indentation on the surface of the material being tested. The Brinell Hardness Number (BHN) is calculated from the measured diameter of the indentation. Barcol Hardness Test is mainly used for very soft materials like plastics to provide quick and easy measurement. Vickers Hardness Test is employed over a wide range of materials from very soft to very hard ones. This method uses a square-based diamond pyramid indenter. Just like Vickers Hardness Test, Knoop Hardness Test uses a rhombic-based diamond pyramid indenter, often used for thin films and brittle materials. Shore Durometer measures the hardness of rubber and plastics with the use of a spring -loaded indenter. The Scleroscope measures hardness by the rebound height of a diamond-tipped hammer that is dropped onto a material.

II. Literature Review

Iloabachie, et al (2017) Investigated the effect of particle size on the flexural strength, ultimate tensile strength, density and water absorption characteristics of uncarbonized coconut shell/unsaturated polyester composites of particle size 425 microns sample and 170 microns sample and the result indicated that maximum flexural and ultimate tensile strength were attained at 20wt% for the 425 microns sample. Elbadawi, et al, (2015) Found high mechanical properties, when the effect of adding a blend of tannins to commercial urea formaldehyde (UF) on

the particleboard made from wood particles of *Acacia seyal* var. *seyal* using the British Standard European Norm (BSEN) relevant standards as compared to the ones produced by solely urea formaldehyde (UF). Iloabachie, Obiorah, and Anene, (2018) Studied the effects of carbonized coconut shell (CS) volume fraction on mechanical properties of unsaturated polyester resin (UPR) composite and found that the mechanical properties tests results show that flexural strength and elongation at break increased as coconut shell proportion got increased. Tensile strength of Teak Wood Saw Dust – Cashew nut shell liquid resin composites was studied by preparing a composite material using a hand layup technique by varying the quantity of the Cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) resin and keeping the saw dust quantity constant by simple methodology of just increasing the percentage of (CNSL). Tensile strength test on the composites using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) according to the ASTM D638 showed that tensile strength of the sample with the highest percentage of (CNSL) was the highest and that the tensile increased with increase in (CNSL), (Ganesan and Valarmathi, 2014). The conclusion to be drawn is that increase in the cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) percentage improves the tensile strength of the composite. As a result of research recently conducted on experimental analysis of flexural strength of wood composite (plywood) in Nigerian commercial sector (Ilo, Ajibo, and Dim, 2025b) revealed that Viewpoint plywood recorded 4.956 N/mm^2 , Plywood EQ recorded 9.467 N/mm^2 while Caledonian, also a make of plywood in Nigerian market recorded 16.973 N/mm^2 as the maximum stress, modulus of rupture (MOR) each of them can withstand while being bent before failing or rupturing.

It was observed that coconut fibre reinforced HDPE has 28.6 mega pascal as optimum value for flexural strength while studying performance characteristics and reinforcement combinations of coconut fibre reinforced high density polyethylene (HDPE) polymer matrixes at optimum condition of volume fractions and particle sizes of coconut fibre-filler (Ihueze, Achike, and Okafor, 2016).

Valle, (2020) Conducted a test for the potentials of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) such as plastic films from packaging as resins for saw dust from coconut lumber for the production of wood-plastic composite (WPC) particleboard when the boards were prepared from 50%-80% by weight of LPDE to sawdust content, both physical and mechanical properties of WPC evaluated showed that the tensile strength, face screw holding and modulus of rupture meet the minimum specifications of the US standards. The study also revealed good interfacial adhesion between sawdust particle and LDPE reduced thickness swelling and improving moisture resistance by diminishing hygroscopy hence expanding the utilization of composites from agricultural wastes and plastic wastes for industrial applications, especially in moist environments, even as well as marine use and humid environment. Through the study of effects of carbonization on the physical and mechanical properties of coconut shell particle reinforced polyester composite, carbonized coconut shell particle reinforced composite recorded the least density value making it desirable in light weight material application, (Iloabachie, et al, 2014).

A study on the properties of developed composite corn cob (CC) and sawdust (SD) particle boards using 100%, 75%, 50%, 25% and 0% variations for both agricultural wastes using formaldehyde as binder at constant

volume reveals that for both physical and mechanical properties the panels with 50% CC had the most preferred performances, (Akinyemi, Afolayan, and Oluwatobi, 2016). Taguchi robust design was applied while studying the optimization of hardness strengths response of plantain fibres reinforced polyester matrix composites (PFRP) and observed that empty fruit bunch fibre reinforced polyester matrix composite has the maximum hardness strength of 19.062 N/mm² which depended greatly on the reinforcement combinations of control factors (Okafor, Ihueze, and Nwigbo, 2013). Evolution of surface properties of concrete through measured lightness and absorption was analysed in the study of panel frameworks and it was found that changes were observed on surface quality after 50 reuses with oriented strand board (OSB) panels formworks while modification of surface quality was noticed after 80 reuses with marine plywood formworks, (Courard, et al, 2012).

While a study was conducted on the influence of activated carbon filler on the mechanical properties of wood composites, a higher strength value of medium density fibreboards (MDF) composites samples than plywood composites samples was revealed because of the increasing thickness of the activated carbon filler (Aziz, et al, 2015). Upon the analysis of the effect of carbonization temperature on wear rate behaviour of rice husk ash reinforced epoxy composites, wear behaviours of 9500C carbonized ash were better than those of 8500C and 9000C carbonized ash due to the degree of alteration in the structure of silica (Ozioko, 2011). A study of flexural strength of medium density fibreboard (MDF) wood composite in Nigerian market shows that SGK Nordic had the best ultimate flexural strength of 13.568 N/mm², Richard Russel had ultimate flexural strength 12.986 N/mm² while MDF Hokusan (MDF) recorded 1.24 N/mm² (Ilo, Nwanjoku, and Olayeye, 2025). Ilo, Nneji and Igede, (2025) Studied the flexural strength of high density fibreboard (HDF) wood composite in Nigerian market with results revealing that Joubert (HDF) recorded 15.604 N/mm², Dabar (HDF) recorded 32.604 N/mm² while Sinoply (HDF) recorded 39.248 N/mm² of their flexural strength at peak. Joubert, Dabar and Sinoply recorded their peak flexural strength at 0.2473%, 0.3769% and 0.7979% strain respectively.

Obviously, it is evident from the summary of reviewed literature with regards to their hardness that research has not been directed towards providing technical information on hardness of wood composites (plywood) in Nigerian market, hence the need for this research paper.

III. Research Methodology

Material

Survey was made in Nigerian market on frequently used wood composites (plywood). From the survey made, most common and three wood composites (plywood) in top demands were identified in Nigerian market. They were selected as samples for analysis. The wood composites (plywood) samples were View Point, Caledonian and Plywood EQ. They are represented accordingly in table 1.

In table 1, the samples are marked “e”, “f” and “g” representing View Point, Caledonian and Plywood EQ respectively. They are all prepared according to the requirement by the machine and tested on the machine one after the other.

TABLE 1 Wood Composites (Plywood) Samples Tested

Sample	e	f	g
Make	View Point	Caledonian	Plywood EQ

Equipment

The Leeds hardness tester as seen in figure 1 which is a portable non-destructive machine for measuring hardness, a type of dynamic hardness test. The Leed hardness value (HLD) is based on the rebound velocity of usually a small impact body which is the indenter after it strikes the surface of the material. The indenter component of the tester is placed on each sample and device gadget clicked; the indenter pushes to make an indent on the sample.

Diligently prepared according to the requirement by the leeds hardness tester in figure 1, the samples (e) representing View Point, (f) representing Caledonian and (g) representing Plywood EQ were all tested on the machine one after the other. Operated by placing the indenter of the Leeds hardness tester and clicking the control button, the Leeds hardness tester indenter pushes forward to make an impact on the sample by indenting on it. The operation is repeated four times for a particular sample (make). With computer program, the dynamics of the action of the indenting and the associated resistance, Leed hardness (HLD) plots are generated. Obviously, the plot which is a function of the sample’s composition resulting from their nature is a clear indication of relationship between force per unit area and the extent of the impact (indent) in the sample. The plots generated are analysed under results and analysis below.

Fig. 1: Leeds Hardness Tester

IV. Results and Analysis

For each of the samples View Point, Caledonian and Plywood EQ, the results of the tests are shown as plots in figures 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Basically, the hardness test results in HLD are for the tested samples of the three selected wood composites (plywood).

Plots

The figure 2 below is a plot for hardness test result of View Point sample. The first test recorded 435 HLD, the second recorded 491 HLD, the third recorded 437 HLD while the fourth recorded 463 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests are taken and reported in the figure 5 for a comparative analysis.

Fig 2: Graph of Hardness Test Results for View Point Wood Composite (Plywood) in HLD

The figure 3 below is a plot for hardness test result of Caledonian sample. The first test recorded 384 HLD, the second recorded 418 HLD, the third recorded 389 HLD while the fourth recorded 439 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests are taken and reported in the figure 5 for a comparative analysis.

Fig. 3: Graph of Hardness Test Results for Caledonian Wood Composite (Plywood) in HLD

The figure 4 below is a plot for hardness test result of Plywood EQ sample. The first test recorded 464 HLD, the second recorded 469 HLD, the third recorded 444 HLD while the fourth recorded 460 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests are taken and reported in the figure 5 for a comparative analysis.

Fig. 4: Graph of Hardness Test Results for Plywood EQ Wood Composite (Plywood) in HLD

The figure 5 below is a plot for aggregate average of the four hardness tests result on View Point, Caledonian and Plywood EQ samples. View Point recorded 456.5 HLD, Caledonian recorded 407.5 HLD while Plywood EQ recorded 459.25 HLD.

Fig. 5: Graph of Aggregate Average of Hardness Test Results for View Point, Caledonian and Plywood EQ in HLD

V. Conclusion and Recommendation

In an ascending order of their hardness test results, Caledonian achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 407.5 HLD, View Point achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 456.5 HLD while Plywood EQ achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 459.25 HLD. Comparatively in terms of hardness, Plywood EQ is 0.6024% and 12.6993% harder than View Point and Caledonian respectively. View Point is also 12.0245% harder than Caledonian. These are as obtained from the result of the tests. The implication of this revelation is that View Point is harder than Caledonian while Plywood EQ is harder than View Point. It is worthy to note that the difference in hardness between Plywood EQ and View Point is small compared to the difference in hardness between Plywood EQ and Caledonian which is as much as 51.75 HLD. Depending on application, choice of wood composites (plywood) from Nigeria market can leverage on this novel technical data with respect to their hardness potentials. Engineers, building contractors, individuals, construction companies as well as furniture makers should value this novel technical insight. Biomedical equipment developers can as well tap on this knowledge. Future research works in wood composites should be channelled towards hardness tests of marine board wood composites, medium-density fibreboard and high-density fibreboard in Nigerian market.

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